

**OPPORTUNITIES TO TRAIN ADMINISTRATIVE STAFF IN THE
HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM**

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Abstract: In this article, the possibilities of training management personnel in the higher education system the essence is illuminated. An analysis of the synergy (connection) between the training of management personnel and socio-pedagogical equipment is given when management is trained, their decision-making process enhances the integration of socio-pedagogical equipment into the academic curriculum .

Key words : innovation, management, control and analysis, experience, projects, decisions, news, efficiency, activity, human economic, technological, assessment.

The progress of any higher education institution largely depends on the quality of its management and the tools it uses to facilitate the learning process. Management staff training and socio-pedagogical aspects are two central pillars in this regard. Together, they provide a comprehensive and effective education while meeting the socio-cultural and personal development needs of students.

In a world where the need to train management personnel is rapidly developing, higher education institutions are not only centers of academic education. They serve as important hubs for community change, critical thinking, innovation and stimulating research. Thus, management plays an important role in ensuring that the organization is aligned with the vision and needs of society.

Effective management ensures proper allocation of resources, curriculum development, research facilitation and overall academic excellence. In addition,

management decisions shape the learning experience of students, which trains management staff to carry out these responsibilities competently.

1. *Leadership Development* : Leadership skills are essential to ensure the effective functioning of an institution. Training programs should focus on building a leader's ability to develop strategy, motivate, and motivate their teams toward organizational goals.
2. *Strategic Planning and Implementation* : Training in this area includes techniques for predicting trends, planning for the future, and effectively implementing strategies.
3. *Financial management* : Proper budgeting, allocation of funds and financial planning are important for the proper functioning of HEIs. Management should be trained to manage the financial affairs of the institution wisely.
4. *Human resource management* : From faculty recruitment to their ongoing professional development, understanding the dynamics of human resources is critical. Management talents bring up and save staying qualified to be need
5. *Modern education technologies about concept* : Numerical education tools and platforms appear to be with managers education experience increase for the most efficient technologies acceptance to do and current reach according to training need

Socio-pedagogical equipment : education social needs with social - pedagogical sharing equipment , essentially , education social sciences with unifying tools , methodologies and approaches is a set . They are personal to grow promotion , socio - cultural to understand development and to students complicated social dynamics to manage help to give for intended .

1. *Cultural equipment* : This tools and methodologies to students different cultures to understand and respect that they do provides . Cultural exchange programs , global traditions according to seminars and the world management history according to courses like events cultural to understand development can

2. *Social mutually effect tools* : Academy and real the world between the difference eliminate reach for OTM students society with directly communication to do possible has been to the platforms need Practice , community service and social research projects this about great is a tool .

3. *Emotional and psychological tools* : Students between aggression , stress and another spiritual health problems like getting stronger going problems with socio-pedagogical equipment too emotional prosperity provide need Advice services , peers support groups and spiritual health according to seminars this needs to satisfy help gives

4. *Moral Education Modules* : In a diverse world with multifaceted challenges, ethical reasoning comes to the fore. Seminars on moral dilemmas, courses on moral philosophy, and platforms that promote moral debate ensure that students are not only academically sound, but also morally sound.

Synergy (relationship) between the training of management staff and socio-pedagogical equipment can strengthen the integration of socio-pedagogical equipment into the academic curriculum when management is trained competently.

For example, a manager trained in modern educational technologies can implement digital platforms that facilitate cultural exchange. Another skilled in human resource management may recognize the need for more consultants or specialists in socio-pedagogical tools.

In addition, managers with a deep understanding of community needs can ensure that institutional goals are aligned with broader societal goals. Such harmony ensures that students are not only prepared for their personal careers, but also become responsible, ethical and valuable members of society.

High education management The role of employees is administrative from tasks out comes out They are of the institute own in his mission current , progressive and efficient to be which provides leader is strength . Successful management according to training strong socio -pedagogical equipment with

combined without , OTMs students professional to success and meaningful social to activity who prepares whole education offer to do can The role of education is increasing expanded going period such synergy is not only dream done , maybe important important have

So, the development of education and its radical change were determined in the following directions: radical democratization of education, further development of continuous education, expansion of the scope of goals and tasks of education. We mentioned methodological approaches to management in our research. These approaches include systematic, situational, task, and quantitative approaches. The principles of regular planning of activities, flexibility of the leading team, mutual understanding and cooperation, customer control, positive attitude and favorable environment, individual leadership and collegiality were used. In addition, evaluation mechanisms and governance mechanisms were also mentioned and analyzed.

The purpose of higher education is to ensure the socio-economic and cultural development of our people, to prepare highly qualified and competitive students who can work independently in the economic conditions of their choice. It was emphasized that instead of falling into our own shells in the field of education, it is only beneficial for the state to be happy with the country's science, it serves to increase the intellectual potential of an educated person. Pedagogical, psychological, philosophical, scientific literature analysis and research works were studied, problems were identified and ways to solve them were shown.

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